

Statistical Analysis and Quantitative Determination of Antidiabetic Drug Linagliptin: A Novel RP-HPLC Method Approach

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Abstract

Linagliptin is an oral medication for managing type 2 diabetes mellitus. Unlike traditional approaches that use high concentrations of drugs with non-volatile buffered solutions and isocratic mobile phases, this is the first approach to introduce an extremely low concentration of linagliptin using a rapid reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) technique. It employs a C₁₈ (5 μ m, 250 mm \times 4.6 mm) Shimadzu GIST column, maintained at 30°C. The mobile phase A contains 0.1% formic acid, while acetonitrile serves as mobile phase B, with gradient elution applied. The flow rate is 1.0 mL/min, and the injection volume is 10 μ L. Detection occurs at 227 nm using a Photo diode array (PDA) detector. This method was validated for key parameters in accordance with the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q2(R2) guidelines. It shows linearity from 0.5 to 3.0 μ g/mL, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9999 ($R^2 > 0.999$). Recovery studies with pharmaceutical tablets indicated 99.98% accuracy for linagliptin. The method demonstrated good reproducibility, with intra-day and inter-day relative standard deviation (RSD) values of 0.56% and 0.4% (%RSD \leq 2). The detection limit (LOD) and quantification limit (LOQ) for linagliptin are 0.043 and 0.132 μ g/mL, confirming the high sensitivity of the method. The quantitative analysis of marketed tablets yielded 99.89% (98-102%) with a RSD of 0.2%. Overall, this analytical method provides reliable, interference-free results, especially significant given the absence of an official monograph in the pharmacopeia.

Keywords—Linagliptin, RP-HPLC (PDA), Method development, Method validation, ICH Q2(R2) Guidelines, Assay

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin, or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it makes to regulate and control blood sugar levels. Elevated blood sugar levels, or hyperglycemia, are a hallmark of uncontrolled diabetes, causing damage to nearly every system in the body, including the blood vessels and the nerves [1].

The chemical name of linagliptin (as per IUPAC) is 1H-Purine-2,6-dione, 8-[(3R)-3-amino-1-piperidiny]-7-(2-butyn-1-yl)-3,7-dihydro-3-methyl-1-[(4-methyl-2-quinazoliny) methyl]. Its empirical formula is $C_{25}H_{28}N_8O_2$, and it has a molecular weight of 472.5 g/mol [2]. The chemical structure of Linagliptin is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Linagliptin

Linagliptin is white to yellow in its solid state and found to be slightly hygroscopic. It melts at 190 to 195°C. It shows very low solubility in water, i.e., 3.33 mg/L at 25°C; however, it is highly soluble in Methanol and slightly soluble in ethanol. It is stable when used as directed, but highly reactive when it comes into contact with strong oxidizing agents [3].

The US FDA approved linagliptin for the treatment of Type 2 diabetes mellitus on May 2, 2011 (Boehringer Ingelheim-1356) for use as monotherapy or in combination with other drugs (e.g., metformin) [4].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive review of the existing literature shows that only a limited number of validated analytical RP-HPLC methods have been reported for quantifying Linagliptin, whether as a standalone compound [5-14] or in combination with other pharmaceuticals, including binary [15-23] and tertiary [24-26] mixtures. The graphical representation of the previously reported method for estimating Linagliptin and its combined dose formulation is shown in Figure 2. Table 1 compares the proposed method with previously reported methods.

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of previously reported RP-HPLC methods of Linagliptin

Linagliptin has not yet been included in any pharmacopeia, making it essential to develop a simple, fast, and accurate analysis method. Previous RP-HPLC methods used high concentration, non-volatile buffers in isocratic mode, requiring thorough washing after a few runs to preserve peak sharpness. In this approach, the lowest concentration with an economical

volatile buffer using gradient elution is employed, enabling rapid system setup and improved reproducibility compared to other methods.

Table 1. Comparison with the previously reported RP-HPLC method for estimating linagliptin.

Sr. No.	Author Name	Conc. Range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Inj. Vol. (μL)	Detector \pm Detection \pm Elution	Accuracy \pm Precision (% RSD)	LOD \pm LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Assay/RSD (%)	Ref. No.
1.	ul Alam <i>et al.</i>	80.0-120.0	10	294 \pm UV \pm Isocratic	100.46 \pm 1.2	1.17 \pm 3.14	100.3 \pm NA	[5]
2.	Rajbangshi J. C. <i>et al.</i>	40.0-60.0	20	PDA \pm 239 \pm Isocratic	100.47 \pm 0.37	0.05 \pm 0.15	NA	[6]
3.	Furqan S. <i>et al.</i>	40-60	20	PDA \pm 239 \pm Isocratic	100.47 \pm 0.37	0.05 \pm 0.15	NA	[7]
4.	Archana M. <i>et al.</i>	12.5-75.0	20	PDA \pm 226 \pm Isocratic	99.64 \pm 0.55	0.9 \pm 2.95	NA	[8]
5.	Zubair Md. <i>et al.</i>	10.0-50.0	20	PDA \pm 238 \pm Isocratic	99.79 \pm 1.2	1.65 \pm 4.98	100.08 \pm NA	[9]
6.	Avinash C. <i>et al.</i>	10-50	20	DAD \pm 238 \pm Isocratic	99.66 \pm 0.8	0.17 \pm 0.54	100.91 \pm NA	[10]
7.	Khaladkar V. B. <i>et al.</i>	10.0-30.0	20	UV \pm 295 \pm Isocratic	99.7 \pm 0.64	NA	97.75 \pm 0.6	[11]
8.	Bagudu L. R. <i>et al.</i>	5.0-30.0	20	UV \pm 241 \pm Isocratic	99.1 \pm 0.48	0.025 \pm 0.08	99.25 \pm NA	[12]
9.	Mourad S. <i>et al.</i>	1.0-50.0	50	DAD \pm 225 \pm Isocratic	100.27 \pm 0.29	0.3 \pm 1.0	100.78 \pm 0.35	[13]
10.	Ganorkar A. V. <i>et al.</i>	1.0-10.0	20	PDA \pm 292 \pm Isocratic	100.71 \pm 0.71	0.53 \pm 1.62	99.0 \pm NA	[14]
11	Proposed method	0.5-3.0	10	PDA \pm 227 \pm Gradient	99.98 \pm 0.8	0.04 \pm 0.13	99.89 \pm 0.2	-

(NA= Not announced, PDA= Photodiode Array, DAD= Diode Array Detector, UV= Ultra Violet)

This study aimed to develop an innovative, rapid, and more convenient RP-HPLC method for the quantification of Linagliptin at lower concentration ranges. This optimized method was thoroughly validated as per the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q2(R2) guidelines [27].

III. METHODOLOGY

Materials and Reagents:

Linagliptin API procured from BLD Pharmatech (Lot No. CHC410, Hyderabad, India) Pvt. Ltd. Commercially available tablets of linagliptin (Linaworth 5 mg, Lot No. LGN12/313/20, Marketed by Dr. Morepen[®] Limited, New Delhi) were purchased from a local pharmacy (Ahmedabad). Formic Acid, Sodium dihydrogen phosphate, Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, and Ammonium Acetate were of AR grade and used as received. Acetonitrile (Batch No. 8782710325, HPLC grade), a 0.45 μm (Batch No. BM4EB1556A), and a 0.2 μm (Batch No. MNN2025104) nylon PVDF filter were purchased from Thermo Fisher Sci. Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai), Merck (Bangalore), and Micro separations (Ghaziabad), respectively. Ultrapure water was used in experimental studies.

Instruments:

The HPLC system used was a Shimadzu 2050C 3D I Series (Batch No. L22986102628, Japan), equipped with a PDA detector, a quaternary solvent pump, a thermostated autosampler, a degasser, and a column oven set at 30°C. Analysis was performed using a C₁₈ (5 µm, 250 mm × 4.6 mm) Shimadzu GIST column (Batch No. 1040166024031L06, Japan), and LabSolutions software was used for data acquisition. An additional instrument included a double-beam Shimadzu 1800 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Japan), a high-precision Shimadzu UniBlockAP weight balance (Model No. D316407364, Japan), a centrifuge machine (D Lab Sci. Corp., China, Batch No. D1010), a sonicator (Bioneds Scientific Corp., Ahmedabad), a filtration pump (Althea Tech., Thane), and a water purifier (ELGA PureLab® flex 1, UK).

Preparation of Blank Solution:

Freshly prepared acetonitrile: water (8:2), sonicated for 10 minutes. It is used as a blank and also as a diluent throughout the chromatographic analysis.

Standard stock solution (1000 ppm):

Linagliptin API (100 mg) was weighed and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Then, 60 mL of diluent was added and sonicated for 10 minutes. This solution was diluted up to the mark with diluent, mixed well, centrifuged for 2 min, and filtered through a 0.45 µm nylon PVDF filter paper to obtain a 1000 ppm solution. This solution was used for any further dilution of the standard solution to a lower concentration.

Sample stock solution (50 ppm):

Ten tablets of linagliptin were taken and crushed with a glass mortar to obtain a fine powder. Take an amount of this fine powder equivalent to 5 mg into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Add 60 mL of diluent, and sonicate the solution for 10 minutes. Make up the solution to the mark and centrifuge well for 2 minutes. Filter through a 0.45 µm nylon PVDF filter and obtain a 50 ppm concentration solution. This solution was used for any further dilution of the standard solution to a lower concentration.

Preparation of mobile phase B (100% Acetonitrile):

Precisely measure and transfer 1000 mL of acetonitrile (ACN) into a clean mobile phase reservoir. Sonicate the solvent for 10 min to effectively eliminate any dissolved air bubbles.

Preparation of mobile phase A (0.1% Formic acid):

Accurately took 1 mL of Formic acid with the help of a graduate pipette and added it to the 1000 mL ultrapure water. Sonicate the solution for 10 min to eliminate the remaining air bubbles.

Solution for UV spectra study:

Take 1 mg of linagliptin, dissolve it in 1 mL of diluent, and prepare a blank solution. The solutions were filtered through a 0.2 µm nylon HPLC syringe filter and scanned in a UV spectrophotometer within the range of 700-190 nm, and also confirmed using a PDA detector while injecting both the standard and sample solutions. The method for wavelength detection is not reported in any pharmacopeia yet. The UV spectrum of standard solutions is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. UV spectrum of Linagliptin

Method development and Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions:

To develop the analytical method, different chromatographic conditions were tested to achieve well-resolved, sharp peaks with acceptable resolution time and tailing factor within the accepted limits. A series of trials was conducted by examining the column type, mobile phase type, ratio, pH, and flow rate. The final column was chosen based on the best peak symmetry, retention time, and reproducibility. Summary of the chromatographic condition development trials is shown in Table 2, and the chromatogram of Several trials is shown in Figure 4(A-H).

Table 2. A summary of the development of chromatographic condition trials

Mobile Phase	Mobile Phase Mode	Column	Flow Rate (mL)	Injection Volume (μ L)	Column Temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)	Mobile Phase pH	Peak Elution Conc. (%)	Observation	Results
ACN: Water	Isocratic	Zorbax C ₁₈ (250*4.6 mm, 3 μ m)	1.0	10	25	NM	-	No peaks	Rejected
AA: ACN	Isocratic	Zorbax C ₁₈ (250*4.6 mm, 3 μ m)	1.0	5	25	7.2	(75:25)	Multiple peaks	Rejected
AA: ACN	Isocratic	Zorbax C ₁₈ (250*4.6 mm, 3 μ m)	1.0	5	25	7.0	(90:10)	Multiple peaks	Rejected
NaH ₂ PO ₄ : ACN	Gradient	Zorbax C ₁₈ (250*4.6 mm, 3 μ m)	1.5	10	30	6.3	(28:72)	Multiple peaks	Rejected
KH ₂ PO ₄ : ACN	Gradient	Kromasil C ₁₈ (150*4.6 3 μ m)	1.5	10	30	3.2	(90:10)	Single peak with tailing	Rejected
0.1%FA: ACN	Gradient	Kromasil C ₁₈ (150*4.6 3 μ m)	0.8	10	30	2.2	(67:33)	Single peak At the front	Rejected
0.1%FA: ACN	Gradient	Kromasil C ₁₈ (150*4.6 3 μ m)	0.8	10	30	2.2	(30:70)	Single peak with splitting	Rejected
0.1%FA: ACN	Gradient	Shimadzu GIST C ₁₈ (250*4.6 5 μ m)	1.0	10	30	2.2	(90:10)	Single Sharp peak	Accepted

(Abbreviations- NM; not measured, ACN; Acetonitrile, AA; Ammonium Acetate, FA; Formic Acid, NaH₂PO₄; Sodium dihydrogen phosphate, KH₂PO₄; Potassium dihydrogen phosphate)

Fig. 4. (A-H). Chromatographic Development Trials

Method Validation Parameters:

Chromatographic methods have been validated according to the analytical procedures recommended by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH). [27] The proposed method was validated for linearity, specificity, precision, accuracy, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), and robustness. Based on this, a concentration range of 0.5–3.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was selected for validation.

Specificity refers to the method's ability to accurately measure the analyte without interference from other expected components, making it one of the most important features of the HPLC method. The specificity of the method was evaluated by injecting blank, standard, and sample solutions separately and recording their chromatograms using the proposed method.

From the stock solution, various aliquots of standard solution, corresponding to 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of linagliptin, were transferred into a series of volumetric flasks, and the volume was adjusted with diluent. Additionally, the solutions were filtered through a 0.2 μm nylon HPLC syringe filter and injected into the HPLC column. Subsequently, calibration curves were plotted with area against concentration, and the regression equations were determined for linearity.

To assess the sensitivity, the method's LOD and LOQ were calculated using the following formulae based on the calibration curve.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

$$LOQ = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where, σ = Standard deviation from the calibration curve and S = Slope of calibration curve.

The accuracy of the chromatographic method was determined by spiking three different amounts of Linagliptin standard into the sample solution. The standard was added to the sample solution at 80%, 100%, and 120% of the drug content. The solutions obtained were filtered through a 0.2 μm nylon HPLC syringe filter before being injected into the chromatographic system. The % recovery values of the added standard amount and % RSD were calculated. Triplicate tests were performed for each concentration.

The precision of the chromatographic method was evaluated based on the intra-day and inter-day reproducibility of the method. Intra-day reproducibility was assessed by determining the % RSD of the peak areas obtained from three injections of the standard solution (2.0, 2.5, 3.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) on the same day. For inter-day reproducibility, the same standard solution was injected once in three consecutive days. Calculate % RSD by evaluating the area.

Final evaluation of robustness was achieved by making some small deliberate changes to the method parameters. It was carried out on three replicates of the standard drug solution (0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The effects of adjusting the flow rate (± 0.2 mL/min), mobile phase composition ($\pm 2\%$ ACN), and wavelength (± 2 nm) were studied. One parameter was changed per trial to assess its effect on the retention time, peak area, and % RSD.

Solution stability:

To evaluate the stability of the drug solution, this test was conducted. The sample (2.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was kept in contact with the diluent at laboratory temperature (24°C) for 5 min, 24 h, 1 week, and 2 weeks. Calculate the average area and % RSD.

Assay of marketed formulation:

Twenty tablets of linagliptin were crushed with a mortar and pestle to obtain a fine powder. From this fine powder, weigh an amount equivalent to 5 mg and transfer it into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Add 70 mL of diluent and sonicate the solution for 10 minutes. Make up the solution to the mark. Filter it through a 0.45 μm nylon filter to obtain a solution with a 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration. After preparing the solution, discard the first 10 mL, and then inject the sample into the HPLC system six times. Inject a standard sample having a 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration and measure the area for calculation of the assay test.

$$\text{Actual weight} = \frac{\text{Sample Area}}{\text{Avg. Sample Area}} \times \text{Label Claim}$$

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{\text{Area of Sample}}{\text{Area of Standard}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of Standard}}{\text{Dilution of Standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of Sample}}{\text{Actual Weight of Sample}} \times \frac{\text{Potency}}{100} \times 100$$

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Method development:

Standard solutions of Linagliptin at a concentration range of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were scanned using a UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800) across a wavelength range of 700-190 nm. The UV spectrophotometer and PDA detector both showed the highest λ_{max} at 227 nm and selected this wavelength for the entire analysis.

Method development is the key part of analysis. It was assessed by the nature of the functional group, as well as the polarity of the drug molecule. The optimized chromatographic conditions for analyzing Linagliptin are detailed in Table 3. These parameters were carefully optimized to ensure accurate analyte separation, support precise quantification, and reduce overall analysis time while providing consistent and reliable results.

Method validation:

The developed chromatographic method was validated for specificity, system suitability, linearity and range, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, and robustness parameters according to ICH guidelines. An overview of the validated parameters is shown in Table 4.

Table 3. Overview of Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Parameters	Conditions
Column	C ₁₈ (5 μm, 250 mm × 4.6 mm) Shimadzu GIST
Mobile Phase	A=0.1% Formic Acid, B=Acetonitrile
Elution Mode	Gradient
Gradient Program [Time (min)/Conc. MP-B (%)]	0.10/5, 1.50/5, 6.00/90, 8.00/90, 8.10/5, 12.00/5
Diluent	Acetonitrile: Water (8:2)
Retention time (min)	7.104 ± 0.1
Flow rate (mL/min)	1.0
Injection volume (μl)	10
Wavelength (nm)	227
Column oven temperature (°C)	30
Autosampler temperature (°C)	15
Run time (min)	12

Table 4. Overview of Method Validation

Parameters	Result
UV detection (nm)	227
Range (μg/mL)	0.5-3.0
System suitability (% RSD)	0.29
System precision (% RSD)	0.32
Intra-day precision (% RSD)	0.56
Inter-day precision (% RSD)	0.40
Accuracy (mean % recovery)	99.98
LOD (μg/mL)	0.043
LOQ (μg/mL)	0.132

A comparison between the chromatograms of the mobile phase blank, the standard solution (API), and the sample solution (Tablet) was performed to evaluate the method's specificity, as shown in Figures 5, 6, and 7, respectively.

Fig. 5. Chromatogram of Blank

The system suitability test was a crucial part of method development and was employed to verify the proper performance of the chromatographic system. Area (A), number of theoretical plates (N), and tailing factor (T) were assessed for six replicate injections of the drug at a concentration of 2.5 μg/mL. The results are presented in Table 5. All values fell within acceptable limits.

The correlation coefficient value for linagliptin indicated a strong relationship between peak areas and concentrations. Therefore, the developed method was linear within the concentration range of 0.5-3.0 μg/mL. Table 6 shows the chromatographic data for linearity, while Figures 8, and 9 display the calibration curve and the overlain chromatogram, respectively.

Fig. 6. Chromatogram of Standard

Fig. 7. Chromatogram of Sample

Table 5. Result of System Suitability

Injection No.	Peak Area
1	155670
2	155201
3	154914
4	155486
5	154631
6	154548
Mean	155075
SD	456
% RSD (≤ 2)	0.29
Theoretical Plates (≥ 2000)	21618
Tailing Factor (≤ 2)	1.1

The significance of the intercept: the 95% confidence interval of the intercept should include zero, indicating that the intercept is statistically insignificant. ANOVA testing (Analysis of Variance) for linearity assesses the probability that the observed regression result occurred by chance. A low p-value for F-test confirms the validity of the regression output (Table 7).

The sensitivity of Linagliptin was evaluated using the proposed method based on the limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD and LOQ were determined according to the signal-to-noise ratio. The results are presented in Table 8.

The average recovery percentages ranged from 99.75% to 100.12%. It was observed that the % RSD value was 0.71, which was the maximum. The results will be displayed in Table 9.

Table 6. Chromatographic Data of Linearity

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Injection Vol. (μl)	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area (mAU)
1	0.5	10	7.104	37184
2	1.0	10	7.125	65419
3	1.5	10	7.115	95228
4	2.0	10	7.115	124693
5	2.5	10	7.115	155343
6	3.0	10	7.115	185874

Fig. 9. Overlain Chromatogram of Linagliptin

Six injections were performed using the proposed analytical method to assess the system's precision. Table 10 shows the recorded values. The % RSD was $\leq 2\%$, the tailing factor was ≤ 2 , and the number of theoretical plates was ≥ 2000 , indicating that the system is repeatable. Intra-day method precision was calculated as the % RSD of results from three samples analyzed on the same day, while inter-day precision was assessed by comparing results over three different days. The % RSD was calculated and found to be within the acceptable criteria of ≤ 2 , as shown in Tables 11 and 12, respectively.

Table 7 Data from the Regression Statistics and ANOVA test for linearity

Parameter	Result
Observations	6
Regression equation ($y = mx + c$)	$Y = 59582 * X + 63552$
Slope (m)	59582.04
Intercept (c)	63552.47
Correlation coefficient (R^2) ($R^2 > 0.999$)	0.9999
Standard Error	848.04
F	21596.38
P-Value (P < 0.05)	0.001293
SD intercept	789.47
Significance F	1.28E-08

Table 8. Result of Sensitivity

Parameter	S/N Ratio
LOD	0.043
LOQ	0.132

Table 9. Result of Accuracy

Level	Preparation	Concentration (ppm)	Spike Recovery (ppm)	% Recovery	% Avg. Recovery	SD	% RSD
80%	1	2.0	2.005	100.25	100.07	0.18	0.2
	2		1.998	99.90			
	3		2.001	100.05			
100%	1	2.5	2.490	99.60	99.75	0.59	0.6
	2		2.510	100.40			
	3		2.481	99.24			
120%	1	3.0	3.010	100.33	100.12	0.71	0.7
	2		2.980	99.33			
	3		3.021	100.70			

Table 10. Result of System Precision

Injection No.	Peak Area
1	155620
2	155184
3	154214
4	155486
5	155631
6	155548
Mean	155281
SD	500
% RSD (≤ 2)	0.32

The results of the robustness study indicate that the linearity, accuracy, and recovery of chromatographic methods are not significantly affected by small changes in key method parameters, such as flow rate, mobile phase, and wavelength. The results of the robustness study are presented in Table 13.

Table 11. Result of Intra-day Method Precision

Level	Concentration (ppm)	Time	Avg. Measured Area (mAU)	SD	% RSD
80%	2.0	11:00 AM, 01:00 PM, 03:00 PM. (n=1 each h)	125250	593	0.5
100%	2.5		151960	1325	0.9
120%	3.0		183640	570	0.3

Table 12. Result of Inter-day Method Precision

Level	Concentration (ppm)	Time	Avg. Measured Area (mAU)	SD	% RSD
80%	2.0	Day 1, Day 2, Day 3. (n=1 per day)	125044	194	0.2
100%	2.5		155100	157	0.1
120%	3.0		187636	1771	0.9

Table 13. Result of Robustness

	Level	Avg. Measured Area (mAU)	% RSD
Proposed method	0.5 ppm	37184	0.32
Flow Rate (mL/min)	+0.2	40134	0.3
	-0.2	48647	0.9
Mobile Phase (%)	+2	65632	0.7
	-2	53935	1.2
Wavelength (nm)	+2	75484	0.6
	-2	99118	0.8

Solution stability:

The stability of the drug sample (2.5 µg/mL) was determined by keeping it in contact with the diluent at Laboratory Temperature (24°C) for 5 min, 24 h, 1 week, and 2 weeks. The result is shown in Table 14.

Table 14. Solution Stability

Injection No.	Analysis Time (After)	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area (mAU)	Avg. Peak Area (mAU)	SD	% RSD
1	5 min	7.111	155184	155269	168	0.1
2	24 h	7.117	155074			
3	1 week	7.110	155428			
4	2 weeks	7.113	155390			

Assay of the marketed formulation by using the developed chromatographic method:

The resulting area of the standard sample was 2852578 mAU. The assay of Linagliptin tablet was performed using the developed and validated RP-HPLC method, and the drug concentration and potency were found to be 4.98 mg and 99.89% respectively. Table 15 and Figure 10 (A-H) display the results of the assay of the marketed formulation.

Table 15. Assay of marketed formulation

Injection No.	Label Claim Weight (mg)	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area (mAU)	Actual Found Weight (mg)	Potency (%)
1	5	7.115	2898864	4.916	99.78
2	5	7.110	2899672	4.997	99.84
3	5	7.119	2900160	4.998	99.87
4	5	7.097	2910389	5.015	100.21
5	5	7.113	2899001	4.996	99.82
6	5	7.109	2898872	4.996	99.81
Average			2901160	4.986	99.89
SD			4551	0.035	0.160
% RSD			0.2	0.7	0.2

Fig. 10 (A). Chromatogram of Blank, **Fig. 10 (B).** Chromatogram of Standard, **Fig 10(C-H).** Chromatogram of Assay

V. CONCLUSION

To the best of our knowledge, a first RP-HPLC (PDA) method has been developed and fully validated for the quantification of Linagliptin at the lowest concentration range. The technique has proven to be selective, linear, reliable, accurate, precise, and robust, consistently meeting the acceptable criteria outlined in ICH Q2(R2) guidelines. Additionally, the method utilizes a simple and convenient mobile phase composition that is readily available, allowing for quick system preparation. The rapid chromatographic run takes only 12 minutes with peak elution at 7 minutes, facilitating the analysis of a large number of samples in a shorter time. The proposed method was applied to Linagliptin Tablet (Linaworth, 5 mg) to perform an assay test. The obtained result is within the acceptable range (98-102%). Hence, this method is suitable for further implementation in routine quality control analysis of Linagliptin within the pharmaceutical industry, demonstrating its ability to distinguish marketed products and ensuring comparability with other Linagliptin formulations.

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VIII. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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